

IN THE PROCESS OF SCIENTIFIC AND CREATIVE ACTIVITY SOCIAL FACTORS IN THE TRANSFORMATION OF SCIENCE TO VALUE

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Annotation: In the article, scientific and creative activity is clearly manifested through thinking, will, discretion, intellect, logic, creativity, desire, memory, thinking, sensitivity, ability. In this process, the scientist creates new spiritual and material wealth. That is, scientific creativity is a special type of work, its special and highest form. An important mechanism of scientific and creative activity has more coherence with thinking. On the basis of thinking, a person has the opportunity to know the existence in a deep and comprehensive way. In thinking, the signs of objects and events and their legal interconnections, general and specific aspects are clearly displayed.

Key words: Innovation, innovation, Social development, Novation, Moral values, Intellectual activity, invention, ability, discovery.

INTRODUCTION

In the leading scientific research institutions and scientific centers of the developed countries of the world, many studies are being conducted on the emergence of science, its development stages, ethical and axiological boundaries. In particular, the emergence of the science of bioethics in the system of philosophical sciences, not only ethics, but also the researches carried out within the framework of such sciences as medicine, biology, and ecology, gave rise to axiological debates about the similarity of the original foundations of human mental and physical existence. This created the need to reconsider the situation that has arisen in the whole world, the events of global scale, as well as the views on the inevitability of science to serve goodness.

It is very important to create an active social environment that values scientific and creative activity in our society. Support and financing of a scientist, learner, scientific research institution engaged in scientific and creative activities is a requirement of today. On the basis of scientific and creative activity with an innovative basis, the scientist is engaged in studying the microstructure of the object he is researching, as well as introducing innovations into it. In this case, the creation of the innovation will have continuity with its execution. This process is called "innovation stage" in scientific creative activity in science. In heuristic-based scientific and creative activity, the time of discovering a new idea and the appearance of a sample are of particular importance. Also, new ideas in it are getting stronger.

As a result, the spread of these new ideas accelerates and their diffusion into new areas occurs.

In the conditions of Uzbekistan, the development of science develops on the basis of scientific innovations. The innovative process, characteristic of scientific creative activity, is theoretically and empirically related to the transition to a new qualitative state, revision of outdated rules, situations and values. In this sense, the sum of theoretical and empirical

innovations constitutes the innovative integrity of scientific creative activity. Innovation is defined as the fact that a new scientific idea or paradigm has some element of "oldness", something that has been around before. In this way, the innovation created for the first time occurs. This innovation equals invention, that is, a new reality established again. In the second case, special attention is paid to adapting to the times by further improving the previously existing idea or paradigm. Thus, innovation is a necessary basis and ground for foreseeing the laws of development of society and nature as a whole, in the diversity of systems. Indeed, great scientists have left a significant mark on science not only because of their discoveries, but because their work has been an example of innovation and service to truth for many generations of people. That is, the discoveries made by scientists should be made with virtue. However, it cannot be said that all the discoveries made in science served humanity. Because the creation of the atomic bomb caused unprecedented problems for mankind. It can be seen that the discoveries made in science are dialectical in nature. Therefore, it is necessary to increase the responsibility of scientists for their scientific activity. Contemporary science includes methodological and general theoretical problems, middle-level theories, and applied scientific research. At the same time, the structure of science includes not only a complex of relevant institutions, but also social and cultural requirements, which include moral standards in the field of science. There will be moral standards and values within their framework.

The more social development advances with the aid and means of science, the greater the risk of inconsistency in the relationship between scientific knowledge and human values. The importance of moral values related to science in the life of society, in the manifestation of the inner spiritual world of a person, is extremely important. Moral values primarily include moral standards and principles of general value.

Solving the problem of products of intellectual and spiritual activity depends on the methodology used in their research. It should be noted that, at the same time, they are functionally or essentially different from each other, use the same methods of cognition, and the laws of dynamics indicate their commonality or non-commonality. These are primarily about understanding the differences. At the same time, other issues arise due to the interaction between these and their interaction with each other.

In this chapter, the dialectical relationship between social and spiritual institutions, the society of intellectuals, the level of spiritual development of society, and its social conditions, which influence the transformation of science into value, is thoroughly analyzed.

Today, in the process of becoming a value of science, the tasks of increasing the role and efficiency of intellectual activity are gaining relevance. Because the appreciation of intellectual activity means the appreciation of science. In the historical development of humanity, the emergence of science, the active application of scientific knowledge methods to the process of knowledge, and the development of fundamental sciences have become crucial. In general, science is the most important aspect of the human phenomenon. The levels of human development are inextricably linked with the development of science. Human development means the development of science. Therefore, the process of science becoming a value depends on a person's ability to create, master and develop science, and use its results in the way of his own perfection. Therefore, along with creating wide opportunities for intellectual activity, it is necessary to give freedom to this type of activity.

The basis of intellectual activity is creativity and its scientific form. Creativity is a complex and aspiration to understand reality in a unique and unique way. Creativity is an unconscious and complex process that rarely occurs to the human brain, perhaps only once in a lifetime. Man is the main source of any creative activity. A person can increase the real wealth of society only through such creativity, he becomes smarter, kinder, and his spirit rises higher. Scientific creativity is not only a separate activity, but also a way of life, plan and perspective of a person. Everything in the work is mysterious and uncertain, and it rejects old-fashioned views of everyday life, like a flood, from a dialectical point of view.

In the analysis of scientific and creative activity, it performs the functions of concepts such as "creation", "discovery" and "invention". Creating a new idea from a scientific point of view means creating a product of creativity by a scientist.

Invention is a scientist's introduction of significant changes to the objective state of things, events, processes in a unique way. Mere summation of empirical evidence is insufficient to generate theory. This always requires inventiveness that focuses on the essence of the problem. Most inventions are created based on industrial production or daily household needs. In this sense, a person who finds the most economical ways to satisfy people's needs can be called an inventor.

And discovery is something that exists independently of the discoverer, the subject's understanding of the phenomenon. In order to hide from the chaos of the world created on the basis of his experience, a creative person creates a simplified clear image of the world and infuses it with his own experiences. This process is not easy. In this case, the task of creativity is to respond to the demands of history, to find completely new programs of activity. From this point of view, scientific creativity forms a person's knowledge and skills, such as setting a scientific problem correctly and reacting critically to it. Scientific justification of the new idea found by the author means separating the most advanced element of the scientific work performed on the basis of creative activity, which retains novelty, has positive aspects and is significantly different from others. Finding and discovering new sources of meaningful evidence in scientific and creative activity is a bright manifestation of the creative thinking of a scientist, and scientific discovery is its peak.

When a person creates scientific ideas on the basis of creativity, he is convinced that this process is large in size and diverse in character. As a result of the scientist's hard work, heuristic ideas are created. In this sense, although labor appears in creativity as a series of other activities, its results have an empirical and theoretical basis. As a product of empirical knowledge, emotion occupies a special place in scientific and creative activity, and it also has a reproductive basis. That is, in the process of creative research, a person has direct and indirect contact with both the inner and outer world. He also perceives the events in it with his intelligence. Feelings provide an opportunity to systematize impressions based on perception, intuition, and memory. On the basis of scientific and creative research, every person perceives the world anew, feels it more clearly, and understands it more deeply. That is, a person has a wider understanding as a result of constant practice, and his direct participation in events and processes serves to be preserved in memory. Such processes further develop intuitive activity in the human mind.

Creativity is the activity of the subject aimed at discovering or creating something new. It mainly manifests itself in:

- as new knowledge in cognitive discoveries;

- introduction of new pedagogical technologies in the educational system;
- in the creation of facilities in the field of invention;
- in the pursuit of discovering the essence of beauty in artistic activity;
- achieving new achievements in sports, etc.

In the current period, creativity and its product occupy an important place in the life of not only the individual, but also the society. After all, it is creativity that enables a person to have non-adaptive activity (which is the opposite of adaptation to stagnant and stagnant conditions), to feel his own vital energy, to approach reality aesthetically (with a sense of elegance, beauty), to be in positive communication that uplifts the spirits of many around him, even in difficult life conditions. provides the possession of the "courage to live" and those with creative abilities embody the forces that ensure the vitality of society. The German philosopher Immanuel Kant wrote in this regard that "Creativity gives a person pleasure, arouses passion, gives rise to love for life." Also, they become life-giving force of society with their creativity. On the contrary, creative and inactive people accumulate destructive forces that destroy social reality. In this sense, one cannot agree with the opinion that a person is born with a high creative ability. It is true that generation also plays a role in the emergence of talent. But in current philosophical studies, children of unique creatives do not have this ability and, on the contrary, cases where great talents were born from parents who did not have such abilities. This shows that the ability to be creative is actually present in everyone, and this ability remains undiscovered in many cases. Of course, this problem seems not complicated on the surface, in fact, solving it requires knowledge related to the processes taking place in society and having theoretical foundations.

Innovative development of modern scientific knowledge, including achievements in genetics, anthropology, philosophy, cultural studies and other scientific fields, as well as the current needs of spiritual development, inevitably lead to the acceleration of work on this problem. At this point, it is clear that some of the work being carried out in modern science, in particular in genetics (for example, cloning experiments, the use of nanotechnology, transplantology, etc.) is going down a heartless, inhumane path, one-sidedness in the solution of this problem, especially in keeping with the high moral standards provided for in the spiritual culture of a person. The result of artificial transformation work, which consists in deviating from the path of natural development, but in the opposite direction, leads to negative consequences. From this point of view, the discoveries made by scientists should be done with goodness. Not all scientific discoveries have served humanity. For example, the creation of the atomic bomb created unprecedented problems for mankind. It can be seen that the discoveries made in science have a dialectical nature.

Solving the problem of products of intellectual and spiritual activity depends on the methodology used in their research. It should be noted that, at the same time, they are functionally or essentially different from each other, use the same methods of cognition, and the laws of dynamics indicate their commonality or non-commonality. These are primarily about understanding the differences. At the same time, other issues arise due to the interaction between these and their interaction with each other. Therefore, in a particular life, they are intrinsically and interconnected with the solution of the main problems of human existence. The democratic changes taking place in the society at the new stage of development have created opportunities for a free approach to the analysis of theoretical-methodological issues and require a revision of the methodological principles used. Elaboration of this

problem, relying on the accumulated knowledge in philosophical research occupies a special place. Philosophical research also shows that there are mutually exclusive views about the necessity of the same methodological approach.

Scientific and creative activity is clearly manifested through thinking, will, discretion, intellect, logic, creativity, desire, memory, thinking, sensitivity, ability. In this process, the scientist creates new spiritual and material wealth. That is, scientific creativity is a special type of work, its special and highest form. An important mechanism of scientific and creative activity has more coherence with thinking. On the basis of thinking, a person has the opportunity to know the existence in a deep and comprehensive way. In thinking, the signs of objects and events and their legal interconnections, general and specific aspects are clearly displayed.

A creative person is distinguished by the depth of his intelligence, independent thinking, originality of thinking, ability to predict, sharpness of mind, strength of imagination and intuition, diligence and aspiration in work, critical attitude towards himself and intolerance, high moral qualities. A particularly common description of a creative person is given in terms of "ability", "talent", "genius". Geniuses do not come into the world outside of time, on the contrary, they appear at the will of the time based on laws that we cannot understand. The genius describes the phenomena in the depths of reality that the ordinary mind did not understand, did not advance, even advanced, could not reveal due to the lack of skill and talent, and brings the ideas about man and the world to a completely new level. For example, Shakespeare was a genius artist - in his works, he well understood the eternal problems of humanity, the main pillars that keep society as a society, and in each of his works he was able to express them with extraordinary skill with unique sincerity. Geniuses of world science include H. Huygens as a mathematician, physicist and astronomer, Snellius the physicist, Leeuwenhoek the inventor of the microscope, Rembrandt the great artist, and others. Sometimes the translation of scientific concepts into the language of mathematics becomes a tool for scientific discoveries, a means of creating completely new concepts and ideas.

The value of the worldview characteristic of scientific creativity is determined by the unity of its theoretical, practical, purposeful and relational aspects. It means the fusion of consciousness and creativity as a result of unity. Every creative subject in his mind and body can perceive, analyze and apply in his practice, depending on the content, every complex reality related to his activity. Therefore, the structure of the person, as Kant said, consists of his aesthetic, theoretical and practical aspects. A person's worldview indicates his attitude to his value. All contradictions exist in this relationship, and a person solves them with his logical thinking.

69% of the respondents note that family and school play a big role in a person's love for creativity, 51% of the influence of friends, 32% of colleagues, classmates, and 21% of special cultural and spiritual activities of book and youth associations. At the same time, almost 94% of the respondents say that they are engaged in or interested in one or another type of creative activity. It is true that among them, artistic creation is in the leading place (78 percent), only 3 percent of young people are interested in scientific and technical creativity. We specifically studied the answers given to our other questions by young people interested in scientific and technical creativity. We found out that in the family of these young people, either their father or brother is engaged in scientific and technical creativity. Among them, young people who have been influenced by friends or others can be counted on the fingers. It follows that the desire to engage in scientific and technical creativity is awakened by adults in

the family. Interest in scientific and technical creativity in young people is not formed by itself, external deterministic factors - the influence of family and friends take the leading place. The influence of special education and educational institutions is an axiom.

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